

TECHNOLOGY FOR DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: This thesis reflects the study, analysis and development of recommendations for the development of the communicative competence of preschool children, the process of learning the development of the communicative competence of preschool children, the content, form, method, and tools of the technology of developing the communicative competence of preschool children.

Key words: competence, communicative competence, stages of development.

Introduction:

Social and communicative development of preschool children is not only an important component of education, but also a necessary element, without which it is impossible to form a full-fledged personality of the child in the future. Every child is an explorer of the world by nature, and his curiosity knows no bounds, especially in the early stages of development. As he grows up and under the influence of factors such as family, environment, kindergarten, he either retains his childhood spontaneity and continues to be happily connected, exploring the world, or simply with his peers. he cannot build relationships and loses himself. ability to communicate. This problem is especially evident in the modern world, because a 2-3-year-old child prefers computer games to communication, and prefers watching TV to a team game. Thus, he deprives himself of the opportunity to develop communication skills, which ultimately leads not only to a lack of such communication, but also to significant difficulties and problems in the process of socialization.

A child's social and communicative development is a complex process, as a result of which he learns to establish and maintain the necessary relationships with the outside world and people. It is the basis for the formation of the communicative competence of a person in the future, which is a whole set of skills, abilities and knowledge that allow to adequately perceive the surrounding reality and respond to it in the process of communication. In simple terms, the child needs to develop socially and communicatively, so that when he goes to school, enters university or works in the future, he should not have difficulties in communicating with other people and should have full rights. a member of

society. It can be said with full confidence that the process of acquiring communicative competence is long and difficult, so it is necessary to start developing the child in this direction from a young age.

The main goal of preschool socio-communicative development is painless and timely socialization of the child by introducing him to the accepted norms of communication, relationships between peers and elders, as well as common cultural traditions accepted in the family. and the state as a whole. In accordance with the federal state educational standard, each preschool educational institution has a special program, according to which all the goals set in the child's development are achieved. And in this case, the final goal - the socialization of the child - can be successfully implemented thanks to the right tasks, the main of which will be:

Mastering the basic moral norms and values accepted in society. Help the child learn the basic rules of communication with peers and senior members of society. Formation of the child's independence and decision-making ability. Helping the child master the main emotional components of communication - empathy, sensitivity, compassion.

Forming respect in each child for his family, peers, adults and the whole society. Helping the child to form a positive attitude to work and creativity. Forming a child's willingness to work together and have fun. To form the basis of safe behavior in the preschool teacher for his own life and the lives of others and in all spheres of life - at home, in society, in nature. The game is the best method of social and communicative development of a child of any age. Another pedagogue and innovator V. A. Sukhomlinsky said: "*Fairy tales, through games, through unique children's creativity - the right way to a child's heart.*" It is the game that can be a reliable assistant for both teachers and parents in the process of social and communicative development of a child. After all, even for older children, not to mention children, the game has been and remains the leading activity, and communication during the game is an integral part of it.

The great role of game activity and its importance in the life of the child was also assigned by the psychologist L. S. Rubinstein, who noted that only during the game the child not only plays the role of someone else and imitates someone else's personality, but also expands, deepens and enriches his own. . And as a result, it becomes easier to understand the world around him and what is happening in it. However, the game is different and what is interesting for a baby may not interest a 4-5 year old at all. Therefore, play activities should not only be appropriate for the child's age, but also give him a sense of control over the

ongoing events. Only in this case, he not only understands the meaning and all the importance of human relations, but also realizes his place in them. And this already forms the necessary skills and communication experience, which will be useful to him both at this stage and in the future.

So, for young children (2 - 3 years old), simple role-playing games on any topic are "Playing in the store", "Playing doctor", "Playing mothers and daughters", etc. At the same time, it is very important that adults participate in the game - father, mother, grandmother, grandfather, teacher - because adults should show the child how to greet and start a conversation by their example. talk, get what you want or, on the contrary, give up what - later. Thus, social and communicative development is aimed at acquiring knowledge, norms and values that allow the child to feel himself as a full member of society.

The problem of socialization of the young generation is one of the most urgent problems today. A person begins to learn about the world from infancy, and this complex, multifaceted process continues throughout life. In addition, the process of socialization can be carried out both in the process of spontaneous interaction with the outside world and in the process of purposefully introducing a person to social culture. The intensity of this process is not the same in each age period. For example, a small preschool child needs emotional contact and cognitive communication with adults, attention to his questions and the most complete answers to them. At this age, the child needs to communicate with his peers, he has the opportunity to communicate with children in games and teamwork. Also, the child can choose the type of activity according to his wishes. In addition, the foundations of self-awareness are already laid in early childhood.

Conclusion:

In an older preschool child, there is a need for stable friendly relations with peers, emotional closeness with them, respect and sympathy of adults. He can communicate, focuses on relationships in the social world; to have stable relationships with peers to implement games and common interests; demonstrate and use communication skills more flexibly; can recognize his place in the peer group.

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